

To what extent did the 1905 revolution weaken the Tsarist regime in Russia?

The 1905 revolution brought many changes to the tsarist regime that weakened his rule and led to the eventual downfall of the Russian empire. To understand why such event greatly affected the rule of the tsar, we must understand what led to the revolution itself.

Compared to other European superpowers at the time Tsarist Russia was very backward in its economy politics and society. 80 percent of the Russian people were peasants and even though they were freed from slavery in 1861 they still worked and lived in tough conditions that they started resisting against. Their main goal was to gain ownership of the land however the Tsar at that time failed to do so. Many protests arose especially after the large famine of 1901 and 1902 and the years 1903 and 1904 became known as the years of the Red Cockerel which highly undermined the central regime. The secret police Okhrana had the role of suppressing any uprisings in the kingdom however the task became to demandful. Russia at the time was a total Autocracy and was in charge of the Tsar. He controlled the cabinet of ministers and the imperial council which was made up of his closest advisors whom he often didn't follow. Tsar was unfit for his role and came to power at a very young age after the death of his father. He was aware of that stating *"What is going to happen to me and all of Russia? I am not prepared to be a Tsar. I never wanted to become one. I know nothing of the business of ruling."* His weak central leadership also lead to revolution and the weakening of the regime. Lastly, the Russian economy began to industrialize however at a slower rate then in other nations. Only 4 percent of workers worked in the factories where production and machinery were outdated so the Russian industry could not compare to that of other nations. This meant higher salaries and awful working conditions which formed opposition among the workers to the tsar and weakened his regime.

These factors created large instability in 1905 and the events of the Bloody Sunday set the Revolution in motion. On the 23rd of January after a strike in Putilov steel works in St. Petersburg earlier that month sparked strikes throughout the city 20000 protesters have gathered around the Winter palace. They were led by Father Gapon who demanded change to the working conditions and an 8 hour work day. He rallied the crowd saying *"Comrade Workers, tear up all portraits of the blood-sucking Tsar and say to him: Be thou damned with all Thine august reptilian progeny!"*. The protest was peaceful but the government responded with force. The soldiers were ordered to fire at the protestors and over 100 were killed. This sparked tremendous uprisings throughout the empire In June, 1905, the Potemkin Mutiny took place and industrial workers all over Russia went on strike. In October 1905, the railwaymen went on strike which paralyzed the whole Russian railway network. Later that month, Leon Trotsky and other Mensheviks established the St. Petersburg Soviet. Over the next few weeks over 50 of these soviets were formed all over Russia mostly in the larger cities which highly weakened the Tsarist regime as the councils represented a united opposition.

Another factor of the revolution that weakened the Tsarist regime was the defeat in the Russo-Japanese War which made people question the strength of the Russian army. People also criticized the tsar and his cabinet for their catastrophic tactics in the war and their inability to lead. When Port Arthur surrendered and the war was considered lost in March of 1905 the liberal groups at the time demanded a change in government and a constitutional system. This meant that the middle and educated classes of society also started to resist the Tsar which further weakened his regime. When the armistice in the war was signed in September of 1905 with the help of Count Witte and the US President T. Roosevelt the Russian army could return back to the country to help the Tsar put down rebellions. The tsar was convinced that he will be able to handle the situation and that he will still have the support of the majority stating *“Rioting and disturbances in the capitals and in many localities of Our Empire fill Our heart with great and heavy grief. The well-being of the Russian Sovereign is inseparable from the national well-being; the national sorrow is His sorrow”* but he also recognised the severity of the situation. All this discontent and emerging disorder and violence in the country forced the Tsar to publish the October Manifesto on the 30th of October which introduced drastic reform.

Witte, the new Chief Minister, advised Nicholas II to make concessions. He eventually agreed and published Witte's October Manifesto. This granted freedom of conscience, speech, meeting and association. He also promised that in future people would not be imprisoned without trial. Finally he announced that no law would become operative without the approval of the State Duma. As the Duma was only a consultative body, many Russians felt that this reform did not go far enough. Leon Trotsky and other revolutionaries denounced the plan. In December, 1905, Trotsky and the rest of the executive committee of the St. Petersburg Soviet were arrested. Others followed and gradually Nicholas II and his government regained control of the situation. The response to the Manifesto was varied. Russian liberal groups like the Constitutional Democrats (Kadets) welcomed it. So too did Russia's middle classes, who viewed the promised reforms as a great opportunity. On the political margins, however, the manifesto was viewed as a concession rather than a serious reform. For Marxists it marked the gradual transition from feudal tsarism to bourgeois parliamentary democracy. The newly-formed Soviets condemned it as doing little or nothing for impoverished and exploited factory-workers; it was a document of high talk and abstractions that would do nothing to alleviate the suffering of the proletariat. Some dismissed it as a tsarist ploy, an attempt to stave off the revolutionary forces of 1905 while the autocracy regrouped. As it turned out, the last of these assessments was probably the most accurate. The manifesto only really served to buy the monarchy some time by appeasing the moderates. Far-right groups like the black hundreds also opposed the October Manifesto as they saw it as a threat to autocracy and went to the streets to protest.

The 1905 revolution weakened the tsarist regime also due to the large number of political assassinations and radical opposition groups at the time. Grand Duke Sergei Alexandrovich of Russia was assassinated in Moscow that year and members of the Tsarist government were often

the target of opposition groups such as the People's will, Mensheviks and Bolsheviks. Over 2000 political assassinations were carried out by the end of 1905 and the opposition groups only grew in size.

However, the tsar still had the support of the army and the Okhrana which he used to take care of any opposition at the time and his army returning from China gave him an extra protective measure which prevented his regime from being weakened further. The first Duma was formed due to the October Manifesto and was filled with radical opposition to the tsar. The largest was the liberal group Kadets with 182 seats which wanted to create a constitutional monarchy. The tsar however disagreed with the ideas and was keen on changing and limiting the power of the Duma. The Duma further weakened Nicholas's grip on power and when he recognised it's danger he decided to limit its power. He blamed Witte for weakening his rule and "*Cursed the Duma. It's all Witte's fault.*" in his view giving this much freedom to people would eventually undermine him and in 1906 he stated, "*As long as I live, I will never trust that man (Witte) again with the smallest thing. I had quite enough with last year's experiment. It is still like a nightmare to me.*"

Before the first Duma could achieve anything meaningful the Tsar introduced the fundamental laws in April 1906 which limited the Dumas's power and once more made him total autocrat. He formed the laws with the help of his new advisor Stolypin that was put in charge of preserving the power of the tsar after the 1905 revolution. In conclusion many factors of the 1905 revolution weakened the tsar's rule and he could no longer rely on the divine right of kings. A growth in radical ideas and a decline in the influence of the Orthodox Church weakened the tsar. Tsar Nicholas II could no longer expect his people to obey him. With all of the reforms that the tsar implemented, he believed he could reinstate the power of his regime but this was seen as idealistic and was recognized by Witte himself when he stated "*The tragic aspect of the situation is that the Tsar is living in an utter fool's paradise, thinking that He is as strong and all-powerful as before.*"